

Spark plasma sintering for ultrafast lignin carbonization

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Abstract

Biobased carbon materials are emerging as alternatives to fossil-based carbons, but the slow carbonization process remains a major bottleneck for scalability. In this study, spark plasma sintering (SPS) is explored for direct and ultrafast carbonization of softwood kraft lignin. The carbonization was performed using SPS in vacuum where the die acts as a radiation heating element. The heating program employed variable heating rates ranging from 15 to 1000 °C min⁻¹ up to a maximum temperature of 1000 °C, followed by an isothermal hold for three minutes. Consequently, excluding instrument cooling, the total carbonization time ranged from 4 to 70 minutes. Despite markedly shorter process time, the lignin-based carbons had similar properties to what can be produced with a conventional carbonization process at a slower heating ramp at similar final temperatures. The lowest energy consumption (kWh) was observed at the highest heating rate (0.75 ± 0.09 kWh at 1000 °C min⁻¹), and a decrease in the heating rate increased the energy consumption. This study therefore shows that SPS can be a useful carbonization method for producing lignin-based carbon materials in a more time- and energy-efficient manner compared to conventional furnace processes.

Keywords: Biocarbon; pyrolysis; process engineering; energy-efficiency

1. Introduction

Carbon materials are used across a wide range of applications, but they carry a substantial fossil carbon footprint due to reliance on fossil-based feedstocks, and energy intensive production processes. This has spurred interest not only in substituting carbon precursors with renewable feedstock [1], but also in developing new energy-efficient methods that enable more sustainable production routes. Lignin is a promising feedstock originating from lignocellulosic biomass (containing 15 to 39 wt.% lignin). Lignin consists of a network of interconnected aromatic phenylpropanoid units, with a high carbon content (> 60 wt.%). Around 70 million tons of lignin is produced each year, mainly from the pulp and paper industries, where the most predominant chemical pulping process produces different varieties of kraft lignin [2]. Nearly all isolated lignin (98%) is used for energy recovery instead of materials production; however, the high carbon content and aromaticity makes lignin an interesting candidate for replacing fossil-based carbon precursors [3].

One of the most common approaches to thermally convert lignin into carbons is by pyrolysis, in which the lignin is exposed to high temperatures in an inert atmosphere or under vacuum [4]. Even if the mechanism is complex, the pyrolysis behaviour of lignin has been suggested to occur in three general stages. The first stage (< 200 °C) is dominated by dehydration reactions that also includes degradation of terminal functional groups, and branches. Second, the active pyrolysis stage (200 to 450 °C) involves breaking the inter-unit linkages, which results in major decomposition, and rearrangements of the lignin structure. In the final stage (> 450 °C) further decomposition and carbonization of the additional lignin and residues occur [5]. It has also been suggested that the thermal treatment of biomass can be generalized into a pyrolysis (< 1000 °C), carbonization (1000 to 2000 °C), and graphitization stage (> 2000 °C). The two final stages include formation-, growth- and stacking of graphitic

layers [2]. To note, lignin is a non-graphitizable precursor, meaning its intrinsic nature prevents the formation of graphite by heat treatment only, and thus forms hard carbons [2,6].

There are various parameters that affect the final carbon material, such as the lignin feedstock, and the process conditions [2]. Slower heating rates are typically used (5 to 50 °C min⁻¹) as it promotes higher carbon yields while fast pyrolysis promotes more bio-oil formation [4]. Li et al. investigated heating rates between 5 to 20 °C min⁻¹ up to 700 °C, for carbonizing lignin in a fixed-bed reactor. They reported on a difference between the heating rates, where higher chance in gas formation and a lower carbon content were observed with increasing heating rates [7]. It is common to use a carbonization temperature above 1000 °C, and the holding times are often hours long which makes the process time-consuming, and consequently energy intensive [2].

In the search for faster and less energy consuming carbon production routes, advanced ultrafast heating methods such as Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS) (Field-Assisted Sintering Technology, FAST) has gained increased attention to produce non-graphitizable carbons (hard carbons) [2]. SPS is a low voltage sintering technique that uses pulsed direct current (DC) to heat the conductive tools in which the sample is placed. The joule heating is efficient because of the tool properties, and usually voltages < 10 V can generate high current (1 to 10 kA). The process is carried out in a chamber under vacuum or using protecting gas. SPS has the ability of reaching ultrafast heating rates (up to 1000 °C min⁻¹), and high temperatures (up to 2400 °C) with standard graphite tools, and can in addition combine the sintering with mechanical uniaxial pressure. SPS has been used for production of a wide range of materials such as ceramics, [8] porous ceramics [9-10], polymer-based composites [11], and various carbon materials [8]

The use of SPS in the context of biomass, was reported for sintering of wood charcoal in 1998 [12], but it is only recently that SPS for carbonization of biomass has emerged [2]. In

2021, Zhen et al. reported on fabrication of hard carbon anodes from sucrose, glucose, and fructose using SPS [13], and in 2024, Xiao et al. used coconut shells as a feedstock for hard carbon anode production [14]. Zhang et al. reported on production of carbon membranes from delignified balsa wood as ultrafast electrochemical capacitors [15]. Furthermore, SPS has been used for production of battery-grade graphite by catalytic graphitization of starch, chitosan, and cellulose at 1100 °C [16]. However, the literature reports of SPS being employed as a direct carbonization method using lignin as the sole feedstock for the production of porous carbon materials are rare.

In the present work, we investigate SPS for ultrafast production of lignin-based carbons. Different ultrafast heating rates (100 to 1000 °C min⁻¹) were compared to more conventional heating rates (15 to 50 °C min⁻¹) typically used in carbonization furnaces. The main carbonization step was performed isothermally at 1000 °C for 3 minutes. The resulting expanded carbon materials were characterized by gravimetric, spectroscopic and microscopic methods to gain insight on their properties. We also investigated the energy consumption of the process in order to get a deeper understanding of the use of SPS for carbonization.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Carbonization of lignin using spark plasma sintering

The carbonization was performed using a SPS furnace (Dr. Sinter SPS-825, Fuji Electronics, Japan) at the SPS facility at Stockholm University. 2 g softwood kraft lignin (SKL) (obtained from UPM BioPivaTM100, Finland) was pre-pressed in a steel die prior carbonisation using 15 MPa for 30-60 s into a pellet in a diameter of 20 mm. The pellet was inserted in a graphite die with an inner diameter of 30 mm and height of 50 mm. Thin graphite paper protected the inner wall of the die. The die setup was such that there was no uniaxial pressure on the samples and thus the die worked as a carbonization chamber. The process was conducted in vacuum and

controlled with a thermocouple in contact with the outer wall of the die. The on:off, DC pulse sequence was 12:2 as recommended by the manufacturer. The samples were heated with different heating rates: 15, 50, 100, 250, 500, and 1000 °C min⁻¹ (denoted as SKL15, SKL50, SKL100, SKL250, SKL500, and SKL1000 respectively) up to 1000 °C where it was held for 3 min. The SPS records the sintering data: voltage, current, temperature, vacuum level and uniaxial pressure.

2.2. Carbonization of lignin using a conventional oven

To compare the material produced by SPS with that from a conventional furnace, synthesis in a tubular furnace (Carbolite) was carried out. To ensure similar setup as the SPS, a pellet was prepared as described above. The pellet was placed inside a graphite crucible, covered with graphite paper on the inside. The graphite crucible was placed horizontally inside the furnace tube. The pellet was heated to 1000 °C under N₂ flow with a heating rate of 15 °C min⁻¹ and held at the final temperature for 1 hour. This sample will be denoted as SKL-TF.

2.3. Energy consumption

The energy consumption (kWh) was calculated from the power input and the duration of the synthesis. The power input was calculated using the following equation:

$$P = V \times I \quad \text{(Equation 1)}$$

Where P is the average power input (W), V is the average voltage (V), and I is the average current (A). The average voltage and current were extracted from SPS data recorded during the process. To calculate the average energy consumption per kg carbon foam (kWh kg⁻¹), the calculated average energy consumption (kWh) was divided by the mass of the carbon product (kg).

2.4. Yield from feedstock

The yield of the dry lignin powder (wt.%) was calculated using the following equation:

$$Yield (wt.%) = m_2/m_1 \times 100\% \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

Where m_1 is the mass (mg) of the lignin powder (before pelletizing) assumed to have a dry lignin content of 68%, and m_2 is the mass of the final carbon (mg) after sintering.

2.5. Scanning electron microscopy and elemental analysis

The pore morphology was investigated using table top HITACHI-TM3000 scanning electron microscope (SEM) with an accelerating voltage of 15 kV. Elemental analysis was performed through energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) using a Bruker Quantax 70 EDX spectrometer with a silicon drift detector which was coupled to the table top SEM. For the EDS analysis, three points were analysed in each image and the average atom percent (at.%) and the standard deviation was calculated. For the detection of possible iron, SKL50, SKL100, and SKL250 were subjected to elemental analysis by Mikroanalytisches Laboratorium Kolbe in Germany.

2.6. Gas adsorption

The N₂ adsorption isotherms were measured using Micrometrics TriStar Plus II at 77 K. Degassing was performed at 200 °C for 12 h under N₂ flow. The specific surface areas of the samples were calculated based on the Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) theory under p/p⁰ ranges 0.0003-0.09 for SKL-TF, SKL15, and SKL500.

2.7. Powder X-ray diffraction

Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) measurements was recorded using a PANalytical X'Pert PRO diffractometer with CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$) in the 2θ ranges 5 to 70° or 5 to 90°

with a step size of 0.0167° . The carbons were ground to a powder prior the measurements and the measurements were carried out in small deep-well plates. The PXRD diffractograms were plotted between 5 to 70° , and were normalized 0 to 1 before smoothed using the Savitzky-Golay filter method in Origin (Version 2021, OriginLab Corporation, Northampton, MA, USA). The interlayer spacing was calculated according to Bragg's law. The peak position was estimated using Fityk peak-fitting program [17]. The fitting was performed in an active 2θ range between 5 - 60° , and assuming a linear background. The broader peaks were fitted as PseudoVoigt peak functions and the sharp peak (around 26°) was fitted as a Gaussian peak.

2.8. Raman spectroscopy

The Raman spectra were recorded between 500 to 3300 cm^{-1} using a Horiba LabRAM HR 800 Raman spectrometer. A $50\times$ magnification objective, a laser wavelength of 532 nm , and 25% or 50% ND filter was used. The calibration was performed using a silicon wafer. The carbons were ground to a powder prior the measurement. The Raman spectra were plotted and normalized 0 to 1 in Origin. The intensity ratio (I_D/I_G) was calculated from the normalized intensities of the D-band and the G-band.

2.9. Attenuated total reflection infrared spectroscopy

Attenuated total Fourier transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy was done with a Varian 610-IR FTIR spectrometer. The spectra were measured from 389 to 4000 cm^{-1} with a total of 32 scans.

2.10. Transmission electron microscopy

A small amount SKL100 was added to a mortar and pestle along with $\sim 0.2\text{ mL}$ of 96% analytic grade ethanol (Solveco, Sweden). The sample was ground until a visually homogeneous

suspension was obtained. The black suspension was transferred to a vial and ultrasonicated in a water bath for around 30 seconds to disperse the particles. A drop of the suspension was then drop-casted onto a lacey carbon-coated transmission electron microscopy (TEM) grid (Electron Microscopy Sciences, USA) and briefly dried under a heater lamp to remove the solvent. Additionally, the TEM grids were cleaned with a plasma cleaner (Fischione Instruments model 1020) for 7 seconds prior to the spectroscopy experiments.

The high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) images were acquired using a JEOL JEM-2100F transmission electron microscope with a field emission gun operating at 200 keV and a UltraScan CCD camera (Gatan, USA). The image power spectra of the HRTEM images were calculated using the FFT function in DigitalMicrograph. The energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) and electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) measurements were performed using a double aberration-corrected Themis Z electron microscope (Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA) at 300 keV accelerating voltage, equipped with a SuperX EDX system and a GIF Quantum (Gatan, USA). The EELS spectra were measured around the carbon K-edge (~285 eV) with an energy resolution of ~1.8 eV, as determined from the FWHM of the zero-loss peak.

2.11. Thermal characterization

The thermal characterization of the carbon was analysed using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). For SKL15, SKL100, SKL250, and SKL1000 a Discovery TGA, TA instruments in dry air flow from room temperature up to 1000 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ was used. For SKL50, and SKL500 a Perkin Elmer TGA 7 instrument was used with the same parameters, but the sample temperature was measured between 43 °C and 960 °C. To visualize the thermal stability, a video was recorded of SKL100 when being subjected to a butane flame (reaching

~ 983 °C) for 2 min and 10 s. Two thermocouples were used to monitor the heat, one in the front of SKL100 facing the flame and another one inserted in the backside of the foam.

2.12. Density and electrical conductivity

The density and electrical conductivity were estimated for SKL50, SKL100, SKL250, SKL500, and SKL1000 from two synthesized replicate samples where each replicate was cut into 2-4 small cylindrical pieces with diameters between 7–10 mm and thicknesses between 1–4 mm. The density was calculated from the weight and dimensions of the cylinders. The electrical conductivity was calculated from measurements of the sheet resistance ($\Omega \text{ sq}^{-1}$) using a multifunction digital four-probe tester (Hefei Kejing Materials Technology Co., Ltd., Anhui., China) at room temperature. Six measurements were performed per cut carbon foam piece (“cylinders”), except for one piece from SKL50 which was measured 3 times, because the presence of too large air gap. The resistivity (ρ) of the cylindrical pieces was estimated using the following equation [18].

$$\rho = R \times \omega \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

Where ρ is the calculated resistivity ($\Omega \text{ cm}$), R is the measured sheet resistance ($\Omega \text{ sq}^{-1}$) and ω (cm) is the thickness of the sample. The electrical conductivity (σ) is the inverse of the resistivity. The error of the electrical conductivity was estimated using a standard error propagation formula from the calculated resistivity.

The statistical significance of the density change was assessed by calculating the pairwise p -values of the measured densities at each heating rate using the Tukey’s HSD test from the SciPy Python library. The correlation between heating rate, sample density, and the electrical conductivity, was assessed using Pearson correlation matrix, computed using NumPy.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Spark plasma sintering for production of lignin-based carbons

The study aimed to investigate SPS as an ultrafast carbonization process of lignin for producing lignin-based carbons. An overview of the experimental approach is shown in Figure 1a. The SKL powder was cold-pressed to a pellet. The pellet was placed inside a graphite die, and graphite spacers were used to connect the die with the two electrodes in the SPS instrument (Figure 1b). The temperature was controlled using a thermocouple in contact with the die wall. The process was performed through pressureless sintering in vacuum, where the die acted as a heating element. This is achieved by the pulsed DC passes through the conductive graphite die rather than the sample, and the joule heating of the die leads to radiation heat transfer to the sample [19], thus acting similarly to a small carbonization oven. Figure 1c shows a photograph of the heated die inside the SPS instrument during the synthesis at approximately 1000 °C. Various heating rates were investigated ranging from conventional slow pyrolysis from 15 °C min⁻¹ up to ultrafast heating rates, going as high as 1000 °C min⁻¹, with a holding time of 3 min at the maximum temperature of 1000 °C. As known, the overshoot for the final temperature increases when increasing the heating rate. The overshoot for the SPS at the different temperatures varied between 10 to 100 °C, but only for a very short period (less than fifty seconds), and therefore quickly stabilized at dwell the temperature. The longest synthesis therefore lasted for 70 minutes, and the shortest for 4 minutes, excluding the cooling down of the instrument (Figure 1d).

Figure 1. (a) Scheme of the softwood kraft lignin (SKL) carbonization using SPS. (b) Experimental setup in the SPS instrument. (c) Photograph of the heated die at ~ 1000 °C. (d) Thermal profiles using heating rates between 15 to 1000 °C min⁻¹.

3.2. Energy consumption

SPS is considered a more energy-efficient method compared to conventional furnaces because of its efficient heating, ability to combine hot pressing with the fast heating rates, and short synthesis time [13]. Therefore, to get a better understanding of the energy consumption (kWh) of the pressureless sintering using SPS, the power input (kW) was calculated from the average voltage (V) and current (A). The lowest power input was required for the slowest heating rate (2.86 kW, 15 °C min⁻¹), and it increased using a faster heating rates, observing the highest

power input (11.2 ± 1.41 kW) using 1000 °C min^{-1} (Figure 2a). However, the opposite effect can be observed when considering the duration of the synthesis, where 15 °C min^{-1} had an energy consumption of 3.32 kWh, and the ultrafast heating rates 500 , and 1000 °C min^{-1} were estimated to consume 0.90 ± 0.07 , and 0.75 ± 0.09 kWh, respectively (Figure 2b). The fastest heating rates show a larger standard deviation compared to the slower heating rates. It is assumed to be a result of the settings for the digital proportional-integral-derivative (PID) values, which is the process control parameters regulating the power input to maintain the programmed heating profile. It is likely that an optimization of these control parameters for the more rapid heating rates would lead to smaller standard deviations. The same trend can be seen for the energy consumption per kg carbon (kWh kg^{-1}), where the highest energy consumption per kg carbon (6146 kWh kg^{-1}) was observed for the slowest heating rate (15 °C min^{-1}), and the lowest energy consumption per kg carbon (1535 ± 176 kWh kg^{-1}) was observed for the fastest heating rate (1000 °C min^{-1}). The relatively high energy consumption per kg carbon is affected by the relatively low yield (13 to 41 wt.%), and mass of the carbon materials (Table S1, and Table S2). The large variation in the yield for the same heating rates is likely caused by several factors, such as the mass losses of the sample while preparing the pellet and removing the sample from the SPS tools, together with slight variation in the precursor lignin. It is also expected that the yield variation is affected by the strength of the vacuum, as changes in the yield were observed when the instrument had a higher vacuum. The effect of vacuum on the yield has previously been reported by Yousaf et al., that investigated vacuum-assisted carbonization of high lignin content walnut shells using a split tube furnace. The authors observed a decrease of the yield using vacuum instead of N_2 atmosphere [20]. The results indicate that although higher heating rates require greater power input, the overall energy consumption decreases because the synthesis time is significantly shortened.

Figure 2. Electrical heating characteristics as a function of heating rate during SPS carbonization. (a) Power input (kW) and (b) total energy consumption (kWh) recorded for heating rates between 15 and 1000 °C min⁻¹.

Previous studies have examined power input and energy consumption in rapid-heating methods, allowing cautious comparison of SPS with other thermochemical conversion techniques. Zhen et al. reported on similar power input using SPS sintering for different types of pre-treated biomasses with temperatures from 900 to 1300 °C and 20 MPa uniaxial pressure. They also observed a difference between the heating stage (3 to 4 kW) and the annealing stage (1 kW) [13]. Note that to our knowledge there is not any reported comparison between the energy consumption using SPS and conventional carbonization furnaces. Recently, Song et al. reported on the energy consumption carbonizing alkali lignin at 800, 900, and 1000 °C using flash joule heating (FJH) compared to conventional tubular furnace carbonization (TFC). The heating rate for the TFC was 10 °C min⁻¹, and around 250-300 °C s⁻¹ for FJH. They reported that FJH consumed 0.0021, 0.0025, and 0.0026 kWh when carbonizing up to 800, 900, and 1000 °C, respectively, whereas the TFC process consumed 14, 15, and 16 kWh for the same maximum temperatures [21]. Furthermore, it indicates that SPS is a useful method in lowering

the energy consumption and increasing the time efficiency compared to a conventional tubular furnace.

3.3. Carbon morphology

During the synthesis the SKL pellet swelled, forming a porous carbon structure, and the presence of macropores was shown by SEM analysis (Figure 3a-b). To investigate the SPS influence on the carbon microstructure, a control sample was prepared using a tubular furnace (denoted as SKL-TF). SKL-TF formed a porous carbon structure with visible macropores similar to the carbons prepared by the SPS (Figure S1a-b). However, the BET surface area of SKL15 and SKL500 (3 ± 2 and $8 \pm 2 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, respectively) was significantly lower compared to SKL-TF ($849 \pm 33 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$), indicating that the SPS process influences the carbon meso- and microporosity (Table S3, Figure S2). EDS analysis indicated a high carbon and low oxygen content, $> 95 \text{ at.}\%$, and $< 4 \text{ at.}\%$, respectively, as well as $< 1 \text{ at.}\%$ of sodium and sulphur for all samples (Table S4, Figure S3). In addition to this, elemental analysis detected traces of iron (ppm levels) in SKL15, SKL100 and SKL250, which was not visible from the SEM-EDS measurements (Table S5). Such Fe traces are presumably derived from the pre-pressing treatment in an iron-based presser.

Figure 3. Appearance and microporosity of lignin-derived carbons produced at increasing

heating rates (50 to 1000 °C min⁻¹), arranged from left to right. (a) Representative photographs and (b) SEM micrographs.

3.4. Structural analysis

Structural analysis was performed on homogenized carbon powders using PXRD, TEM and spectroscopic techniques. The PXRD pattern shows two broad peaks centered at 24°, and 43° (Figure 4a), which correspond to the (002) and (100) reflections of disordered carbons [6]. A sharp peak centered at 26.4° is visible for SKL250, and SKL1000, but less prominent for SKL15, SKL50, SKL100 and SKL500 (Figure 4a, Table S6). However, for replicates of SKL100 and SKL500, the sharp peak clearly appears (Figure S4, and Table S6) and indicates that there is no systematic trend in its appearance. This peak was not visible in the diffractogram for the pristine SKL (Figure S4) indicating that is caused by the process. It may be some metal salt reacting during the carbonisation although we were not able to identify it. There is also a possibility that it comes from contamination from the SPS graphite tools, although careful handling of the sample, this is further discussed later.

To get further understanding of the carbon structure, Raman spectroscopy was used. All samples show presence of two bands around 1350 cm⁻¹, and 1590 cm⁻¹ (Figure 4b-g), which correspond to the D-band, and G-band, respectively. The D-band comes from breathing modes of *sp*² carbons in rings, and can indicate structural defects, and the G-band comes from bond stretching of the *sp*² carbons. The intensity ratio from these two peaks (I_D/I_G) therefore gives an indication of the level of disorder, and/or defects, as higher levels indicate less degree of graphitization [22]. Figure 4h presents the calculated I_D/I_G values, where it is possible to see that all samples have a ratio > 1, except for one outlier for SKL100, where the value is lower (0.75), indicating structural disorder. The band around 2695 cm⁻¹, visible for one of the

measurements for SKL100 (Figure 4d), and SKL500 (Figure 4f), can be assigned to the 2D peak and indicate increased stacking of carbon layers [6].

Figure 4. Structural characterization of lignin-derived carbons. (a) PXRD patterns of the carbonized samples. Raman spectra of (b) SKL15, (c) SKL50, (d) SKL100, (e) SKL250, (f) SKL500, and (g) SKL1000. (h) Intensity ratio (I_D/I_G) as a function of heating rate (SKL15–SKL1000). (i) FTIR spectra of the SKL precursor and corresponding carbonized samples (SKL15–SKL1000).

The FTIR spectrum (Figure 4i) of the lignin precursor (SKL) exhibits a well-defined doublet in the 854 and 816 cm^{-1} range, which serves as a structural fingerprint of guaiacyl (G) units. The bands at approximately 625 and 670 cm^{-1} are assigned to out-of-plane aromatic ring deformations and C-H bending vibrations (γ C-H), respectively [23-24]. Following carbonization, this doublet disappears completely in all samples (SKL15-SKL1000) regardless of the heating rate (Figure 4i, Figure S5). This signifies the degradation of individual phenolic rings, dehydrogenation, and the formation of a condensed carbon matrix, in which discrete molecular vibrations are replaced by the collective absorption of turbostratic carbons. Simultaneously, the intense oxygen-related bands in the 1000-1200 cm^{-1} zone (C-O in alcohols and β -O-4 ether bonds) vanish, indicating deoxygenation and the removal of methoxy groups [25]. This transformation is further supported by the evolution of the 1600 cm^{-1} band (aromatic C=C stretching), which disappears during thermal condensation [23]. Notably, the FTIR spectra for SKL15-SKL1000 are nearly identical, suggesting a similar surface chemical composition and functional group distribution.

TEM images revealed an overall flake-like morphology of the carbon particles. At higher magnification, a wavy texture with short-range layer stacking can be distinguished, likely corresponding to stacked carbonaceous sheets (Figure 5a-b). This morphology resembles a disordered layered structure, rather than a graphitized carbon material [26]. The absence of crystalline domains is supported by the lack of sharp peaks in the image power spectrum (FFT), shown in Figure 5a. Further evidence is provided by the EELS spectra of the carbon K-edge, which show a clear π^* peak at around 285 eV, followed by a broader peak between 290 and 315 eV (Figure 5c). No clear feature corresponding to the σ^* peak characteristic of graphite is observed. These features are consistent with EELS spectra previously reported for non-graphitized carbon [25-26].

The source of the peaks at 26.4° observed in the XRD patterns (Figure S4, Table S6, Figure 4a) thus remains inconclusive. Although they could correspond to graphite based solely on their position, no clear graphitic domains were observed with TEM. Furthermore, some crystalline regions were found during imaging, but their contribution was ruled out as their electron diffraction patterns generally did not match the XRD peak patterns acquired from the bulk (Figure S6). In addition, they appeared to be well separated from the carbonaceous material that represented the bulk of the sample.

Figure 5. Nanoscale morphology and electronic structure of lignin-derived carbon. (a) Low-magnification TEM image showing a representative carbon particle with flake-like

morphology. (b) High-resolution TEM image of the particle edge, revealing a wavy texture characteristic of amorphous carbon; inset shows the corresponding FFT with diffuse intensity, indicating the absence of crystalline domains. (c) Representative EELS spectrum acquired at the carbon K-edge from a thin region of the particle, with the π^* peak indicated.

3.5. Thermal characterization of the lignin-based carbons

TGA was used to better understand the thermal stability of carbons under dried air flow. SKL15 starts to decompose around 459 °C and is fully decomposed around 636 °C. SKL1000 starts to decompose around 487 °C and is fully decomposed around 577 °C. The TGA data also indicates that the carbon decomposition occurs in two stages for SKL50, SKL100, SKL250, and SKL500 with a second onset approximately around 532 to 593 °C. Whereas it appears that only one weight loss step occurs for SKL15 and SKL1000 (Figure 6a-b, Table S7). Furthermore, to visualize the oxidative stability, a video was recorded when SKL100 was exposed to a blue flame for 2 min and 10 s without igniting. Two thermocouples monitored the temperature: one facing the flame next to SKL100, and one inside an air gap of SKL100. The thermocouples indicated a temperature difference of approximately 763 °C between the inside of SKL100 and the flame, 220 °C and 983 °C, respectively (Figure 6c, Video S1-S2).

Figure 6. Thermal stability and combustion behaviour of lignin-derived carbons. (a) TGA curves of SKL15–SKL1000. (b) Enlarged view of the TGA data between 300 and 700 °C. (c) Selected frames from Video S1 showing SKL100 during exposure to a butane flame.

3.6. Electrical conductivity and density

The electrical conductivity (S cm^{-1}) of the porous structure of the carbons was calculated from measurements of the sheet resistance ($\text{Ohm (cm)} \text{sq}^{-1}$). The carbons were cut into smaller pieces of which the density was also estimated. The carbon density increases from SKL50 to SKL500 (0.043 ± 0.006 to $0.093 \pm 0.023 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ respectively) but decrease again for SKL1000 ($0.054 \pm 0.008 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) (Figure 7a, Table S8). The violin plot in Figure 7a, indicates a lower variance of the density for SKL50 and SKL1000 compared to SKL100–SKL500, which have the data spread over a wider range. However, the difference in density between different heating rates is mostly statistically significant ($p < 0.005$, 95% confidence interval), except between

SKL250 and SKL500 ($p = 0.83$) (Table S9). Furthermore, the electrical conductivity follows the same trend as the density, where the electrical conductivity increased from 0.76 ± 0.84 to $1.62 \pm 0.53 \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, for SKL50 and SKL500, respectively, and decreased for SKL1000, $0.93 \pm 0.25 \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, (Table S8). A linear correlation between the electrical conductivity and the density can also be seen from the correlation heat map (Figure S7), and from Figure 7b, which shows a positive correlation ($R^2 = 0.629$) from a regression analysis. However, it should be noted that the four-point probe measurements require thinner samples than what was mechanically possible to achieve and the porosity gives the samples large air holes which affects the measurements and is the likely the cause for the large spread of the measured electrical conductivity.

Figure 7. (a) Violin plot showing the kernel density distribution of density (g cm^{-3}) as a function of heating rate ($^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$) for lignin-derived carbons produced with heating rates 50-1000 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$. The median and the interquartile range (25-75%) indicated and whiskers represent 1.5 IQR. (b) Electrical conductivity (S cm^{-1}) as a function of density for lignin-derived carbons SKL50-SKL1000.

The electrical conductivity of lignin-derived carbon materials has been widely reported to depend strongly on precursor type, processing strategy, and carbonization conditions [28].

Yan et al. (2021) prepared carbon foams from SKL using a three-step method including molding, foaming, and carbonization. They used the Van der Pauw's four probe technique (using Pt wire and Ag paste on the ends) to estimate the electrical conductivity. They reported the foams to have an electrical conductivity between 700 ± 55 to $2031 \pm 73 \text{ S m}^{-1}$, and observed a dependence of conductivity on the density of the foams [29]. Furthermore, Kane et al. investigated the electrical conductivity on lignin-based carbons and compiled information of the reported electrical conductivity based on different final carbonization temperatures, which suggested a variation from 10^{-2} to 10^2 S cm^{-1} . Electrical conductivity is dependent on various factors, such as raw material, preparation method and synthesis conditions [28]. This shows that SKL50-SKL1000 have a lower electrical conductivity compared to the SKL foams reported by Yan et al., but is within the range expected for lignin-based materials.

4. Conclusions

This study investigated SPS as an ultrafast method to carbonize softwood kraft lignin, where the die worked as a small carbonization oven in the pressureless SPS setup. The process was performed with different heating rates from 15 to $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$, in order to compare more conventional with ultrafast heating rates. A final carbonization temperature of $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a holding time of 3 min was used, making the shortest synthesis as fast as 4 minutes, excluding the cooling down of the instrument. The lignin pellet swelled to a porous carbon material with visible macropores. The structural analysis indicated a disordered structure for all heating rates. The electrical conductivity was in the span for expected values for lignin-based carbons. The energy consumption (kWh) of SPS showed that the fastest heating rates (500 and $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$) had similar energy consumption around 0.90 ± 0.07 , and $0.75 \pm 0.09 \text{ kWh}$, respectively. The highest energy consumption were observed for the more conventional heating rates, 15 and $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$, 3.32 kWh and $1.98 \pm 0.11 \text{ kWh}$, respectively. Thereby, suggesting that an

increase in heating rate lowers the energy consumption for the carbonization process. This investigation therefore indicates that SPS has the potential to be a new advanced ultrafast carbonization method to produce lignin-based carbon materials. However, the SPS techniques for industrial scales are still in development, and potential harmful by-products arising from the thermochemical conversion of lignin should be considered with respect to the intended application and production scale of lignin-derived carbon materials.

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Author contributions

S.T. Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft; M.E. Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review and editing; I.P. Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review and editing; J.Y. scientific discussions, data analysis, Writing - Review & Editing; T.K. Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – review and editing; T.W. Writing – review and editing M.H.S. Project administration, Methodology, Writing – review and editing, Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision.

Declaration of interests

I.P., M.E., and M.H.S. are inventors of a Swedish patent No. 2350988-8 on carbonization of lignin using spark plasma sintering. I.P. is employed by Lignoflow Technologies AB that holds rights to the aforementioned patent. M.H.S. is the chairman of the board of Lignoflow Technologies AB.

Supplementary material

Tables S1–S9 and Figures S1–S7 (PDF). Video S-1 and Video S-2 (flame test).

Data and code availability

The source data for this article will be publicly available upon publication of the article at DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19505067.

Figure captions

Figure 1. (a) Scheme of the softwood kraft lignin (SKL) carbonization using SPS. (b) Experimental setup in the SPS instrument. (c) Photograph of the heated die at ~ 1000 °C. (d) Thermal profiles using heating rates between 15 to 1000 °C min⁻¹.

Figure 2. Electrical heating characteristics as a function of heating rate during SPS carbonization. (a) Power input (kW) and (b) total energy consumption (kWh) recorded for heating rates between 15 and 1000 °C min⁻¹.

Figure 3. Appearance and microporosity of lignin-derived carbons produced at increasing heating rates (50 to 1000 °C min⁻¹), arranged from left to right. (a) Representative photographs and (b) SEM micrographs.

Figure 4. Structural characterization of lignin-derived carbons. (a) PXRD patterns of the carbonized samples. Raman spectra of (b) SKL15, (c) SKL50, (d) SKL100, (e) SKL250, (f) SKL500, and (g) SKL1000. (h) Intensity ratio (I_D/I_G) as a function of heating rate (SKL15–SKL1000). (i) FTIR spectra of the SKL precursor and corresponding carbonized samples (SKL15–SKL1000).

Figure 5. Nanoscale morphology and electronic structure of lignin-derived carbon. (a) Low-magnification TEM image showing a representative carbon particle with flake-like morphology. (b) High-resolution TEM image of the particle edge, revealing a wavy texture

characteristic of amorphous carbon; inset shows the corresponding FFT with diffuse intensity, indicating the absence of crystalline domains. (c) Representative EELS spectrum acquired at the carbon K-edge from a thin region of the particle, with the π^* peak indicated.

Figure 6. Thermal stability and combustion behaviour of lignin-derived carbons. (a) TGA curves of SKL15–SKL1000. (b) Enlarged view of the TGA data between 300 and 700 °C. (c) Selected frames from Video S1 showing SKL100 during exposure to a butane flame.

Figure 7. (a) Violin plot showing the kernel density distribution of density (g cm^{-3}) as a function of heating rate ($^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$) for lignin-derived carbons produced with heating rates 50–1000 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$. The median and the interquartile range (25–75%) indicated and whiskers represent 1.5 IQR. (b) Electrical conductivity (S cm^{-1}) as a function of density for lignin-derived carbons SKL50–SKL1000.

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Supplementary material

Spark plasma sintering for ultrafast lignin carbonization

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This PDF contains:

Tables S1–S9

Figures S1–S7

Table S1. Average energy consumption (kWh) and per kg carbon (kWh kg⁻¹ carbon) for SKL15-SKL1000, and the parameters used, where *t* is the time for the synthesis (h), *I* is the average current (A), *V* is the average voltage (V), *P* is the power calculated from *I* and *V* (kW). The error given is the standard deviation of the replicates for the different heating rates.

Sample	<i>t</i> (h)	<i>I</i> (A)	<i>V</i> (V)	<i>P</i> (kW)	\bar{P} (kW)	Average energy consumption (kWh)	Average energy consumption per kg carbon (kWh kg⁻¹)
SKL15	1.16	1361	2.1	2.86	-	-	-
SKL50	0.38	1616	3.1	5.01	5.16 ± 0.28	1.98 ± 0.11	7101 ± 1773
	0.38	1558	3.2	4.99			
	0.38	1614	3.4	5.49			
SKL100	0.22	1813	3.8	6.89	6.92 ± 0.22	1.50 ± 0.05	6071 ± 2317
	0.22	1865	3.8	7.09			
	0.22	1883	3.6	6.78			
	0.22	2080	3.5	7.28			
	0.22	1847	3.7	6.83			
	0.22	1853	3.6	6.67			
SKL250	0.12	2164	4.0	8.66	9.14 ± 0.42	1.07 ± 0.05	3108 ± 1131
	0.12	2225	4.2	9.35			
	0.12	2140	4.4	9.42			
SKL500	0.08	2580	4.5	11.6	10.9 ± 0.80	0.90 ± 0.07	2372 ± 893
	0.08	2265	4.3	9.74			
	0.08	2386	4.7	11.2			
	0.08	2359	4.6	10.9			
SKL1000	0.07	2254	4.3	9.69	11.2 ± 1.41	0.75 ± 0.09	1535 ± 176
	0.07	2602	4.8	12.5			
	0.07	2430	4.7	11.4			

Table S2. The mass of the lignin powder before pressing m_L (g), mass of the pellet m_p (g) (m_L and m_p represent the actual mass and not the dry powder), mass of the carbon product m_c (g), and the yield from feedstock (wt.%) estimated from the lignin powder (calculated on dry basis as seen in equation 2, section 2.4.). The error given is the standard deviation of the replicates for the different heating rates.

Sample	m_L (g)	m_p (g)	m_c (g)	Yield (on dry basis) (wt.%)	Average yield (wt.%)
SKL15	-	1.78	0.540	-	-
SKL50	2.06	1.85	0.32	22.8	20.8 ± 4.78
	2.06	1.85	0.34	24.3	
	2.01	1.82	0.21	15.4	
SKL100	2.05	1.76	0.32	23.0	21.2 ± 10.7
	2.00	1.67	0.30	22.1	
	2.01	1.74	0.18	13.2	
	2.02	1.77	0.18	13.1	
	2.01	1.71	0.20	14.6	
SKL250	2.00	1.69	0.38	27.9	26.9 ± 8.55
	2.02	1.82	0.48	34.9	
	2.05	1.79	0.25	17.9	
SKL500	2.05	1.86	0.53	38.0	30.0 ± 9.77
	2.05	1.86	0.48	34.4	
	2.04	-	0.22	15.9	
	2.10	-	0.45	31.5	
SKL1000	2.06	1.88	0.48	34.3	35.1 ± 1.79
	2.06	1.90	0.52	37.1	
	2.00	1.68	0.46	33.8	

Table S3. Measured BET surface area of SKL-TF, SKL15, and SKL500.

Sample	BET surface area (m ² g ⁻¹)
SKL-TF	849 ± 33
SKL15	3 ± 2
SKL500	8 ± 2

Table S4. Elemental analysis (at.%) of carbon, oxygen, sodium, and sulphur from EDS analysis of the carbon foams. The error comes from taking the standard deviation of the three measurements.

Sample	Elements			
	C (at.%)	O (at.%)	Na (at.%)	S (at.%)
SKL50	95.6 ± 0.49	3.78 ± 0.48	0.393 ± 0.05	0.273 ± 0.03
SKL100	96.8 ± 0.66	2.32 ± 0.59	0.103 ± 0.14	0.810 ± 0.41
SKL250	96.1 ± 0.34	3.35 ± 0.34	0.233 ± 0.05	0.280 ± 0.01
SKL500	96.0 ± 0.61	3.36 ± 0.61	0.437 ± 0.03	0.247 ± 0.07
SKL1000	95.9 ± 0.56	3.43 ± 0.60	0.407 ± 0.03	0.250 ± 0.03

Table S5. Elemental analysis of iron in SKL15, SKL100, and SKL250.

Sample	Fe (ppm)	Dry (%)
SKL15	504	1.95
	501	1.96
SKL100	464	0.33
	468	0.34
SKL250	460	1.28
	457	1.26

Table S6. The estimated peak position 2θ ($^{\circ}$), and the corresponding d-spacing (nm) for the PXRD patterns of SKL15-SKL100.

Sample	2θ ($^{\circ}$)	d-spacing (nm)
SKL15	23.9	0.37
	43.8	0.21
SKL50	23.9	0.37
	43.7	0.21
SKL100	24.1	0.37
	43.3	0.21
SKL100 (duplicate)	24.0	0.37
	26.4	0.34
	43.7	0.21
	54.4	0.17
SKL250	24.0	0.37
	26.3	0.34
	43.6	0.21
SKL500	24.3	0.37
	43.7	0.21
SKL500 (duplicate)	24.0	0.37
	26.4	0.34
	43.6	0.21
	54.5	0.17
SKL1000	24.0	0.37
	26.3	0.34
	43.5	0.21

Table S7. Summary of the TGA analysis.

Sample	Water content (wt.%)	1rst decomposition			2nd decomposition			Residual mass (wt.%)
		Onset	Endset	Δm	Onset	Endset	Δm	
		(°C)	(°C)	(wt.%)	(°C)	(°C)	(wt.%)	
SKL15	6.7	459	636	91	-	-	-	2.4
SKL50	6.8	512	590	64	590	664	27	2.0
SKL100	6.0	479	593	76	593	660	13	4.6
SKL250	2.8	465	532	33	532	581	61	4.0
SKL500	6.1	513	578	86	578	681	4.1	3.4
SKL1000	3.0	487	577	94	-	-	-	2.8

Table S8. The average sheet resistance R (Ohm (cm) sq⁻¹), resistivity ρ (Ohm cm), electrical conductivity σ (S cm⁻¹), and the density d (g cm⁻³).

Sample	R^a (Ohm (cm) sq ⁻¹)	ρ^a (Ohm cm)	σ^a (S cm ⁻¹)	d^b (g cm ⁻³)
SKL50	7.97 ± 15.2	2.53 ± 5.36	0.76 ± 0.84	0.043 ± 0.006
SKL100	5.26 ± 1.50	0.92 ± 0.35	1.19 ± 0.42	0.065 ± 0.019
SKL250	3.54 ± 1.19	0.79 ± 0.32	1.49 ± 0.51	0.088 ± 0.026
SKL500	2.80 ± 1.01	0.70 ± 0.26	1.62 ± 0.53	0.093 ± 0.023
SKL1000	4.56 ± 1.45	1.18 ± 0.34	0.93 ± 0.25	0.054 ± 0.008

^aThe error is calculated from the standard deviation.

^bThe error is calculated comes from propagation of the resistivity.

Table S9. The p -values from pairwise comparison of the lignin-derived carbon density.

Comparison	p -value
SKL50 – SKL100	8.87×10^{-6}
SKL100 – SKL250	1.57×10^{-4}
SKL250 – SKL500	0.83
SKL500 – SKL1000	1.11×10^{-16}

Figure S1. (a) A photograph, and (b) SEM microgram of a control sample of the lignin-derived carbon using a tubular furnace (SKL-TF).

Figure S2. N_2 gas adsorption/desorption isotherms for SKL-TF, SKL15, and SKL500.

Figure S3. SEM image, and EDS mapping analysis of SKL50 showing the presence of carbon, oxygen, sodium, and sulphur.

Figure S4. PXRD of SKL, and a duplicate of SKL100, and SKL500.

Figure S5. FTIR of a second spot of SKL15-SKL1000.

Figure S6. The HRTEM image + electron diffraction pattern with calculated d-spacings of the reflections.

Figure S7. Linear correlation heat map of the heating rate ($^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$), electrical conductivity (S cm^{-1}) and density (g cm^{-3}) of the lignin-derived carbons.